

MAIN WAYS OF EXPRESSING MODALITY IN THE MODERN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The present article is devoted to investigation of ways of expressing modality in English. This or that meaning is to a great degree determined by communicative type of the sentence and the form of the infinitive. That is a huge problem for foreign learners of English, who make a great deal of mistakes in this field. So, the aim of the work is to show how modal verbs can be used and expressed in different situations and meanings.

Key words: modality, meaning, modal verb, context, model, construction.

The study of language modality and modal verbs - one of the thorniest issues in theory and practice of language teaching. In connection with this problem of differentiation of modal verbs is relevant for the study. Therefore, the central concept of our work is the notion of modality in English, means of expression, the specific use of modal verbs. It is evident that traditional beliefs did not cover the whole fullness of modal verbs as a research problem.

The actuality of the theme of the research is the central concept of our work and the notion of modality in English, means of expression, the specific use of modal verbs determined due to the fact that the investigation in grammatical structure of the modality in the English language plays the great role in studying English as a second language.

The aim of the research is modal verbs are of particular interest to us, because first of all modal verbs are designed to express a purely personal attitude of the speaker to the subject of his speech. In our case, we are wondering the practical application of these verbs in the field of business communication, since at first glance, the scope limits the freedom of verbs by turning them into an element of well-established formal phrases.

The scientific novelty is vivid in the following:

investigation of models of business English correspondence has been fulfilled;

the study of the functional style leads us to the observation that the speaker resorts to a certain functional style due to such extra lingual factors: the character of the situation in which communication takes place (official, ceremonial, informal, private or other);

the relations between the communicants (formal, official, friendly, spontaneous); the aim of communication (transference of specific information, emotional attitudes, establishment of business contacts); oral or written communication have been defined and proved by examples.

The main ways of expressing modality in question are modal verbs, forms of mood, tone and modal words. In the dictionary of linguistic terms is given as the division of the modality by type:

- 1) the modality of the hypothetical, which involves presentation of the contents statements as alleged;
- 2) modal verb - modality expressed by the verb;
- 3) the modality of surreal - presentation of the contents statements as impossible, unrealizable;
- 4) the modality of the negative - view the content of the utterance as inappropriate reality [1, p. 246].

We find the following modal verbs in English: **can, may, must, ought, shall, should, will, need and dare**. Besides, **to have** and **to be** in some of their uses are also classed among modal verbs. A modal verb in combination with the infinitive forms a **modal compound predicate**.

Modal verbs have the following peculiarities:

- 1) they are followed by the infinitive **without** the particle *to* (with the exception of *ought, to have* and *to be*);
- 2) their interrogative and negative forms are built up **without** the auxiliary *do*.

Most of the verbs have more than one meaning. Each of their meanings is characterized by a specific usage.

- 1) Some of the meanings may be found in all kinds of sentences; others occur only in affirmative of interrogative or negative sentences;
- 2) Different meanings may be associated with different forms of the infinitive – simple and perfect (both in the active and passive forms), continuous and perfect continuous;
- 3) If the modal verbs have more than one form (*can – could, may – might, will – would*, also the verbs *to have* and *to be*), their different meanings are not necessarily found in all those forms.

The use of modal verbs is in most cases independent of the structure of the sentence: the use of this or that modal verb is determined by the attitude of the speaker towards the facts contained in the sentence. In this case we may speak of the free or independent use of modal verbs [2, p. 273].

E. g. He admires you. He thinks you're a little beauty. Perhaps I oughtn't to have told you that.

He may be in the hall now, waiting for me.

But sometimes the use of certain modal verbs depends on the structure of the sentence, mainly on the type of the subordinate clause, and occasionally also on the lexical character of the predicate verb in the principal clause. This may be called the **structurally dependent** use of **modal verbs**.

E. g. It is obviously necessary that an investigation should be made.

Christine feared she might not be met at all.

The analysis of modal verbs is made rather difficult by other factors. The point is that their past tense-forms do not often refer to past time at all [3, p. 109]. Such are the verbs *can* and *may*, *shall* and *will*, for instance, which are not easily defined in formal terms of grammar learning. Morphologically they have the present and the past tense-forms, but in modal phrases they are not regularly used to mark time relations. Moreover, to indicate past time does not seem to be their main function. We naturally distinguish different time relations in:

(1) *He can speak English fluently*

(2) *He could speak English fluently when he was a boy.* But there is no **time** difference in many cases like the following:

(1) *He may go* → *He might go.*

(2) *Dark as the night shall be...* → *Dark as the night should be...*

It seems reasonable to characterise the dual nature of the modals used in complex verbal predicates as follows.

Modal verbs may function as a) "fully lexical" verbs expressing ability, possibility, permission, power, admonition, duty, obligation, need, will or readiness to do something associated with the activity of **the** subject, e. g.: *One must do one's duty. Can she speak English? May I come in?* b) modal auxiliaries of weakened predication: *will/would, can/could, may/might, must* and *ought* In this latter case they weaken their original meaning and come to express supposition, logical inference, certainty or uncertainty with regard to the action expressed by the notional verb.

Compare the following:

(a) 1) <i>If I do the thing, I will do it thoroughly, but I must have a free hand.</i> (Galsworthy)	(b) 1) <i>They tell me Jolyon's bought another house... he must have a lot of money — he must have more money than he knows what to do with!</i> (Galsworthy)
2) <i>"I can't tell", he would say: "It worries me out of my life".</i> (Galsworthy)	2) <i>It must be a mistake. She can't be there alone. 3) "Land ought to be very</i>
3) <i>I ought to go there.</i>	<i>dear about there", he said.</i> (Galsworthy)
4) <i>May I come in?</i>	4) <i>I shall be guarded. He may throw some light.</i>

Thus, English modality can be expressed not only by modal verbs. Modality can be expressed by different linguistic means. In actual speech all forms expressing modality work together to make the meaning clear. But in every case there is some leading form that expresses the main attitude. These forms fall into four categories: phonetic (intonation), grammatical (mood), lexico-grammatical (modal verbs), lexical (modal words and phrases). But the most important from them is the third form, which includes modal verbs. It is important to take into account one more feature peculiar to modal verbs. They all show that a certain action is represented as necessary, doubtful, etc. From the point of view of the speaker, there are verbs which ‘help’ other verbs to express a meaning: it is important to realize that “modal verbs” have no meaning by themselves. A modal verb such as would has several varying functions; it can be used, for example, to help verbs express ideas about the past, the present and the future. It is therefore wrong to simply believe that “would is the past of will”: it is many other things.

CONCLUSION

This analysis allowed us to systematize the knowledge of modal verbs and use them for further study in the field of business communication. Based on the examples of the use of modal verbs in speech situations, business communication, we identified a number of peculiarities of the verbs in our chosen field. We have identified these characteristics the use of modal verbs as their frequency, identified a number of the most frequently used verbs, and with it the most commonly used values of the selected verbs. Also, the investigation of our study was to include and determine some of the most frequently used modal values and the definition of the diversity of options for their expression. It should also be noted that, despite the specificity of the business style of communication, yet we can in the process of business communication to show his own attitude toward the seemingly formal and well-established phrases.

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